

1 **Engineered deletion of STING.**

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6 Sting1 likely has functions which remain incompletely defined. We used RNA-sequencing to measure
7 total transcription in HEK293 cells with engineered deletion in *Sting1*. A central molecular consequence of
8 loss of *Sting1* was failure to transduce DNA repair signals through *Rad23b*. *Sting1*^{-/-} cells lost expression
9 of the LPS associated factor *Litaf* and failed to express the lymphotoxin beta receptor *Ltbr*. *Sting* deficient
10 cells activated stem regenerative function marked by induction of *Lgr5*. *Sting* controls immunity through
11 regulation of DNA damage signals, inflammatory effectors, wound healing and regenerative responses
12 together with pathogen sensing in a cell type-dependent fashion.

13 Citations

14 1. Zhang, C., Shang, G., Gui, X., Zhang, X., Bai, X.C. and Chen, Z.J., 2019. Structural basis of
15 STING binding with and phosphorylation by TBK1. *Nature*, 567(7748), pp.394-398.

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